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Research Article

Method Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method For Determination of Selexipag in Bulk and Formulation

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ABSTRACT

The present study described a new, simple, accurate and precise development for estimation of selexipag by RP Agilent Tech. Gradient System with Auto injector, UV (DAD) & Gradient Detector Reverse Phase (Agilent) C18 column (4.6mm x 250mm; 5 μ m), a 20 μ l injection loop and UV730D Absorbance detector and running chemstation 10.1 software. Methanol: water (0.1%OPA), (75:25) v/v, pH 3. was used as the mobile phase for the method. The detection wavelength was 270 nm and flow rate was 0.8 ml/min. In the developed method, the retention time of Selexipag was found to be being 5.268 min. The developed method was validated according to the ICH guidelines. The linearity, precision, range, robustness was within the limits as specified by the ICH guidelines. Hence the method was found to be simple, accurate, precise, economic and reproducible. So, the proposed methods can be used for the routine quality control analysis Selexipag in bulk drug as well as in formulations. The analytical method was validated according to ICH guidelines (ICH, Q2 (R1)). The described HPLC method was successfully employed for the analysis of selexipag. The method provides selective quantification of Selexipag This developed RP-HPLC method for estimation of Selexipag is accurate, precise, robust and specific.

INTRODUCTION

The Project entitled Method development and validation of selexipag in its bulk and dosage forms has not been reported by using RP-HPLC method. Hence, there is a need of new analytical method development for the estimation of selexipag. Aim of work is to develop a new,

simple, fast, rapid, accurate, efficient and reproducible RP-HPLC method by optimizing the chromatographic conditions for the analysis of selexipag and to perform stress degradation studies. The developed method will be validated according to ICH guidelines Q2 (R1).¹ Mechanism of Selexipag is a selective prostacyclin (IP, also called PGI₂) receptor agonist. The key features of

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pulmonary arterial hypertension include a decrease in prostacyclin and prostacyclin synthase (enzyme that helps produce prostacyclin) in the lung. Prostacyclin is a potent vasodilator with anti-proliferative, anti-inflammatory and anti-thrombotic effects; therefore, there is strong rationale for treatment with IP receptor agonists. Selexipag is administered orally; maximum concentration of drug and its active metabolites were observed with the bioavailability of 57% and 29% in rats and monkeys.² Drug material and products are assessed with precision, accuracy, and dependability thanks to the development and validation of analytical methods, which are essential parts of pharmaceutical analysis. Reverse Phase High- Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) has become the most popular method among the several that are available because of its high sensitivity, specificity, repeatability, and robustness³. It is especially useful for assays that indicate stability. Additionally, ICH guideline Q2(R1) lists the parameters linearity, accuracy, precision, specificity, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantitation (LOQ), and robustness that are required for the validation of analytical methods. While some techniques for estimating selexipag using LC-MS and HPLC have been previously reported, many of them are either expensive or lack validation in accordance with ICH guidelines. Therefore, the current study's goal is to create a straightforward, accurate, precise, and validated RP-HPLC method for measuring selexipag in pharmaceutical dosage forms and bulk drugs.^{4,5}

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD:

2.1 MATERIALS

API: Selesipag

- **Solvents and Reagents:** Methanol, Acetonitrile, 0.1% Orthophosphoric Acid,

Water (HPLC grade) 0.1% Acetic Acid (HPLC grade)

- **Marketed Sample:** Selepeg 200 mg tablet

2.2 Preliminary Characterization

Physical Properties

Selexipag: White crystalline powder.

Solubility

- Selexipag is freely soluble in Methanol and poorly soluble in water PH adjusted 0.1% Orthophosphoric Acid, Buffer pH 3.2.

2.3 UV Spectroscopy

- **Solvent:** Methanol
- **Wavelength scan:** 200–400 nm
- **λ_{max} identified:** 270 nm

2.4 Method Development via RP-HPLC^{6,7}

- **Column:** AgilentC₁₈ (250mmX 4.6mm,5 μ m)
- **Mobile phase trials:** Methanol+0.1% (OPA)water,(75:25 % v/v)
- **Optimized condition (Trial 6):**

Chromatographic Conditions:

- **Detector:** U.V. Detector
- **Column:** AgilentC₁₈
- **Column Dimension:** 250mmX 4.6mm,5 μ m
- **Injection Volume:** 20 μ l
- **Wavelength:** 270 nm

- Mobile phase: Methanol+0.1% (OPA)water,(75:25 % v/v)
- Blank and placebo injections confirmed the method's specificity.

- Flow Rate: 0.7 ml/min

- Run time: 15 Minutes

- **Preparation of System suitability test (Selexipag standard solution):**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg Selexipag working standard into 10 ml volumetric flask as about dilute Methanol prepared in completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent to get 1000 µg/ml standard (stock solution) and 15 min sonicate to dissolve it and from the resulting solution 0.1 ml was transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to the mark with mobile phase Methanol:(0.1% OPA) Water solvent.

- The resulting 10 µg/ml of solution was subjected to chromatographic analyses using mobile phases of different strengths with chromatographic conditions.

2.5 System Suitability

2.6 Sample Analysis

- **Formulation:** Selepag 200 mg tablets
- Sample preparation involved methanol extraction, filtration, and dilution with mobile phase.
- % Assay calculated using validated formula.

3. Validation as per ICH Guidelines

3.1 Specificity

- No interference from placebo or excipients.

3.1 Linearity

- Concentration range: 80–120 µg/mL
- Correlation coefficient: >0.998
- %RSD: <2%

3.2 Accuracy (% Recovery)

- Recovery within 98–102% at all levels (80%, 100%, and 120%)
- %RSD: <2%

3.3. Precision

- Six replicates analyzed
- % Assay: 90–110%
- %RSD: <2%

Intermediate Precision

- Performed on different day
- %RSD: <2% across 12 samples

3.4. Reputability

3.3 Limit of Detection and Quantification

- LOD and LOQ calculated from calibration curve:
 - $LOD = 3.3 \sigma / S$
 - $LOQ = 10 \sigma / S$

3.4 Robustness

- **Parameters varied:**

- Flow rate ± 0.1 mL/min
- Temperature $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$
- Wavelength ± 3 nm

- System suitability maintained across variations

3.5 Solution Stability

- Standard and test solutions stable for 24 hours under lab conditions.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Preliminary Characterization and Identification of Drug

4.1.1 Color, Odour, and Appearance

The physical examination of Selexipag revealed that it is a **White to off-white powder (pure API) powder**. These results are in line with the reported physical characteristics, confirming the identity and physical form of the drug.

4.1.2. Melting point

The procured reference standard of Selexipag was found to melt in the range of 134°C respectively

4.1.3. Solubility Study

This study was carried out to find an ideal solvent in which drugs are completely soluble. Various solvents were tried for checking solubility of Selexipag. From solubility studies it was concluded that of Selexipag is freely soluble in Methanol and poorly soluble in water PH adjusted 0.1% Orthophosphoric Acid, Buffer pH 3.2.

4.2. UV Spectral Analysis

4.2.1. Selection of Solvent

UV absorption of $10\ \mu\text{g/mL}$ solution of Selexipag in methanol was generated and absorbance was taken in the range of 200-400 nm. $270\ \text{nm}\ \lambda_{\text{max}}$

4.2.2. Selection of Analytical Wavelength

1) Blank Methanol

Figure. No.1: UV spectrum of Methanol as a blank

2) selexipag standard solution

Figure. No. 2: UV spectrum of Selexipag

Standard solutions were scanned in the range of 200-400nm, against 10 ml methanol and volume make with methanol solvent system as reference. Selexipag in methanol was found to be 270 nm, selected wavelength is 270 nm.

4.3. Method Development by RP-HPLC

4.3.1. Optimization of Chromatographic Conditions

The final chromatographic conditions selected were as follow:

- **Analytical column:** Agilent C₁₈ Column (250mm x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m particle size).
- **Injection volume:** 20 μ l
- **Flow Rate:** 0.7 ml/min
- **Mobile Phase:** Methanol: water (75: 25 % V/V)
- **Detection:** 270 nm
- **Run Time:** 15 min

Figure. No. 3: Typical chromatogram of Trial 6

Thus, from the six trial it has been observed that, using mobile phase of Methanol+0.1% (OPA)water,(75:25 % v/v),PH 3.,270 nm, Flow rate 0.8 ml gave adequate retention at 5.268 min with good peak shape (Theoretical plates Selexipag 12255)

4.4. System Suitability Test

All five replicate injections of the standard solution passed the system suitability criteria:

- % RSD of area: **0.05%** (Limit: NMT 2.0%)
- Theoretical plates: **>15000** (Limit: NLT 2000)
- Asymmetry: **1.13–1.14** (Limit: <2.0)

These results confirmed the system’s suitability for routine analysis.

Table No.1: Repeatability studies on Selexipag (HPLC)

Sr. No.	Concentration of Selexipag (mg/ml)	Peak area	Amount found (mg)	% Amount found
1	40	1313.9235	40.41	101.02
2	40	1310.9528	40.39	101.00
		Mean	40.40	101.01
		SD	2.10	2.10
		%RSD	0.16	0.16

Repeatability studies Selexipag was found to be 101.01%, the %RSD was less than 2, which shows

high percentage amount found in between 100% indicates the analytical method that concluded.

Figure No.4: Chromatogram of System suitability No- 2

4.4.1. Analysis of Marketed Test samples (Assay)

a) Selepag 200 mg Tablet

b) Total weight of 20 tab Powder wt. = 63.12 gm

c) Avg. Powder Weight = 315.6 mg

- d) Eq.Wt for 10 mg= $10 \times 315.6 / 200 = 15.78$ MG
 e) Take 15.78 mgs in 100 ml Methanol i.e. = 1000 µg/ml tab solution -TAB STOCK –II

Table No.2: Result for standard Chromatogram of Selexipag

No.	RT [min]	Area[mV*s]	TP	TF	Resolution
1	5.321	358.03867	12504	0.86	-

Figure No.5: Chromatogram of standard Selexipag

4.5. Method Validation:

4.5.1. Solution Stability

Standard and test solutions were stable at room conditions for **up to 24 hours**, with % absolute differences well below 2.0%.

4.5.2. Specificity

No interference was observed at Selexipag retention time from blank or placebo solutions, confirming specificity.

4.5.3. Linearity and range

Table No 3. Linearity of Selexipag (HPLC)

Sr. No.	Concentrationµg/ml	Area Selexipag
1	10	358.86
2	20	667.03
3	30	995.09
4	40	1304.84
5	50	1606.57

Table No 4. Regression equation data for Selexipag

Regression Equation Data Y=mx+c	
Slope(m)	31.33
Intercept(c)	46.50
Correlation Coefficient	0.999

Linearity of of Selexipag was observed in the range of 10-50 µg/ml. Detection wavelength used was 270 nm. The calibration curve yielded correlation coefficient (r^2) 0.999 & 0.999 for Selexipag respectively

4.5.4. Accuracy (Recovery Study)

1) Accuracy (Recovery)

Recovery studies were performed to validate the accuracy of developed method. To pre analyzed Tablet solution, a definite concentration of standard drug (80%, 100%, and 120%) was added and then its recovery was analyzed .Statistical validation of recovery studies shown in

Table No 5: Result of Recovery data for Selexipag

Drug	Sr No.	Level (%)	Amt. taken (µg/ml)	Amt. Added (µg/ml)	Area. Mean* ± S.D.	Amt. recovered Mean *±S.D.	%Recovery Mean *± S.D.
HPLC method	1	80%	10	8	17.95±0.01	7.96± 0.01	99.56±0.24
	2	100%	10	10	20.04±0.06	10.0±0.06	100.3± 0.64
	3	120%	10	12	21.84±0.03	11.84±0.03	98.67± 0.25

*mean of each 2 reading

Table No. 6. Statistical Validation of Recovery Studies Selexipag

	Level of Recovery (%)	Mean % Recovery	Standard Deviation*	% RSD
HPLC	80%	99.56	0.24	0.24
	100%	100.39	0.64	0.63
	120%	98.67	0.25	0.26

*Denotes average of three determinations.

Chromatogram:

Figure. No. 6 Chromatogram of Accuracy 80%

Figure. No.7 Chromatogram of Accuracy 120%-02

Data interpretation: Recovery of analytical procedure was found well within acceptance criteria

The method was established by analyzing various replicates standards of Selexipag. All the solution was analyzed thrice in order to record any intraday & inter-day variation in the result that concluded. The result obtained for intraday is shown in table respectively.

2) Precision

Table No 7: Result of Intraday and Inter day Precision for Selexipag HPLC

Conc ⁿ (µg/ml) HPLC	Intraday Precision			Interday Precision		
	Mean± SD	%Amt Found	%RSD	Mean± SD	%Amt Found	%RSD
10	354.01±1.46	98.15	0.41	354.31±0.17	98.25	0.05
30	991.50±9.19	100.54	0.93	995.87±7.72	101.01	0.78
50	1604.30±0.19	99.44	0.19	1630.51±14.42	101.12	0.88

***Mean of each 3 reading**

Intraday and Inter day Precision for Selexipag which shows the high precision %amount in between 98% to 102% indicates to analytical method that concluded.

Chromatogram:

Figure No. 8: Chromatogram of Precision

Figure No.9: Chromatogram Inter-day precision (50mcg)

3) Robustness

To evaluate the robustness of the proposed method, small but deliberate variations in the optimized method parameters were done. The effect of changes in mobile phase composition and flow rate, wavelength on retention time and tailing factor of drug peak was studied. The mobile phase

composition was changed in ($\pm 1 \text{ ml/min}^{-1}$) proportion and the flow rate was varied by of optimized chromatographic condition. The results of robustness studies are shown in table. Robustness parameters were also found satisfactory; hence the analytical method would be concluded.

Table No.8 Result of Robustness Study of Selexipag

Parameters	Conc.($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount of detected (mean \pm SD)	%RSD
Mob-phase composition(74ml+26ml)Methanol + 0.1% (OPA)water	50	1612.0 \pm 3.08	0.19
Mob-phase composition(76 ml+24ml) Methanol + 0.1% (OPA)water	50	1615.6 \pm 2.66	0.16
Wavelength change 269nm	50	1623.7 \pm 11.15	0.69
Wavelength Change 271 nm	50	1588.77 \pm 10.78	0.68
Flow rate change(0.7ml)	50	1842.38 \pm 2.24	0.12
Flow rate change(0.9 ml)	50	1431.78 \pm 0.32	0.02

Chramotogram:

1) Flow Rate Change 0.9 ml

Figure. No. 10 Chromatogram of Flow rate change 0 Mobile phase composition

2) Change: 74ml Meoh + 0.1 % (OPA) 26 ml Water

Figure No .11 Chromatogram of Mobile phase composition change 74ml Meoh

+0.1 %(OPA) 26mlWater

3) Wavelength Change 269 nm

Figure. No 12: Chromatogram of comp change wavelength change 269 nm

Data interpretation: The changes were did flow rate ($\pm 1 \text{ ml/ min}^{-1}$), PH of mobile phase composition, and Wavelength. %RSD for peak area was calculated which should be less than 2%.the result shown in analytical method that concluded.

4. Limit Detection

The LOD is the lowest limit that can be detected. Based on the S.D. deviation of the response and the slope the limit of detection (LOD) may be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LOD} &= 3.3 (\text{SD})/\text{S} \\ &= 3.3 \times 1.25 / 31.33 \\ &= 0.1303 \end{aligned}$$

Where, SD = Standard deviation of Y intercept

S = Slope

- The LOD of Selexipag was found to be 0.1303 ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) analytical methods that concluded.

5. Limit Quantification

The LOQ is the lowest concentration that can be quantitatively measured. Based on the S.D. deviation of the response and the slope,

The quantitation limit (LOQ) may be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LOQ} &= 10 (\text{SD})/\text{S} \\ &= 10 \times 1.25 / 31.33 \\ &= 0.3949 \end{aligned}$$

Where, SD = Standard deviation Y intercept

S = Slope

- The LOQ of Selexipag was found to be 0.3949 ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) analytical methods that concluded.

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

Selexipag is Anti-hypertensive agent, The present work deals with “Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for estimation of Selexipag in Bulk Drug And it’s Dosage form”

5.1 Summary for HPLC method:

Attempts were made to develop RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Selexipag from Tablet. For the RP - Agilent Tech. Gradient System with Auto injector, UV (DAD) &

Gradient Detector Reverse Phase (Agilent) C18 column (4.6mm x 250mm;5 μ m), a 20 μ l injection loop and UV730D Absorbance detector and running chemstation 10.1 software.

Methanol: water (0.1%OPA), (75:25) v/v, pH 3.was used as the mobile phase for the method. The detection wavelength was 270 nm and flow rate was 0.8 ml/min. In the developed method, the retention time of Selexipag was found to be being 5.268 min. The developed method was validated according to the ICH guidelines. The linearity, precision, range, robustness was within the limits as specified by the ICH guidelines. Hence the method was found to be simple, accurate, precise, economic and reproducible. So the proposed methods can be used for the routine quality control analysis Selexipag in bulk drug as well as in formulations.

5.2 Conclusions for HPLC method:

- 1) The method provides selective quantification of Selexipag This developed RP-HPLC method for estimation of Selexipag is accurate, precise, robust and specific.
- 2) The method has been found to be better than previously reported method, because of its less retention time, isocratic mode and use of an economical and readily available mobile phase, readily available column, UV detection and better resolution of peaks

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